

Solutions to Perfect the Policy of Supporting Livelihoods for Farmers in Thai Nguyen Province, Viet Nam

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Abstract:

Household farmers play an important role in developing the agricultural sector and ensuring the food security of each country. Therefore, the support of the central government and Thai Nguyen provincial government is of great significance. The article has pointed out solutions to improve livelihood support policies for farmers in Thai Nguyen province.

Keywords: Policy, Farming households, livelihoods, Thai Nguyen province.

1. Introduction:

In Thai Nguyen province, Vietnam today, the number of farm households accounts for a relatively large proportion (48.9%) in 2020 (Thai Nguyen Provincial Statistical Office, 2021), but the quality of human resources of farm households in the province is not high. Besides, the resources of land, credit, social capital and material resources are not high. Therefore, the central government and the provincial government have policies to support the livelihoods of farmers in the province. However, the policy still faces some limitations in terms of criteria: transparency, systematicity, relevance, effectiveness, feasibility, effectiveness, fairness and level of implementation. policy goals. Therefore, the article has proposed some solutions to improve livelihood support policies for farmers in Thai Nguyen province, including: perfecting policies to support livelihood contexts, perfecting financial support policies. Livelihoods, perfecting policies to support livelihood transformation and perfecting support policies to ensure livelihood outcomes.

2. Solutions to perfect livelihood support policies for farmer households in Thai Nguyen province.

2.1. Completing policies to support livelihood context (product consumption support policy).

Currently, the policy of supporting product consumption for farmer households in Thai Nguyen province has achieved certain achievements; especially the province has been proactive in applying technology in bringing products of products. Households meet Occop and VietGAP standards on e-commerce postmart and voso.vn. However, the consumption of products of farmer households still faces many difficulties in the context of the current COVID-19 pandemic and the implementation of policies is inadequate. Therefore, the thesis proposes some solutions to improve the policy of supporting product consumption for farmers in Thai Nguyen province.

Firstly, for linking parties in the implementation of production links associated with agricultural consumption, the province needs to have legal documents to clearly define the responsibilities of the parties when participating in the link.

For farmer households in Thai Nguyen province when participating in the link chain, to receive support for the output market and access to market information, they need to commit to producing and selling agricultural products. According to the signed contract. However, in production and business activities, for maximum profit goals, farmer households are willing to break those commitments without binding legal documents.

For businesses and cooperatives, the lack of binding sanctions is one of the reasons why they are willing to break the commitments of product consumption for farmers. This greatly affects their livelihood results later. It is necessary to improve propaganda activities for farmers, businesses and cooperatives so that they are aware of the role of complying with commitments when participating in the link chain.

Secondly, the digitalization of farmer's agricultural products on e-commerce is an inevitable trend not only to help farmers access the domestic market but also in the international market, thereby improving. Livelihood results for farmer households. To do this well, Thai Nguyen province needs to build a good

information technology platform and need to build a team of experts from the province to support farmers in maintaining and operating on e-commerce. Good. The provincial support should be implemented not only in the period of the plan but also until farmers can master the digital platform. In addition, changing the sales method related to the habits and ideology of farmers, so in documents related to the implementation of digital transformation, the province is not only directional. Technically leading that it is necessary to integrate into the propaganda of ideology for farmers.

Third: It is necessary to further promote the role of industry associations in participating in planning and promulgating policies related to supporting agricultural goods consumption in Thai Nguyen province. Industry associations will provide information and demand for consumption of the market so that the provincial People's Committee has made appropriate adjustments in the planning of production of agricultural products. Market forecasting is an important stage, bad forecast is the cause of influence on the output market and livelihood results of farmer households. Farmers are at risk of being forced to price when they are crops and lack of supply when crop failure. The provincial People's Committee needs to cooperate with the Departments of Industry and Trade, the Department of Finance ... to assess the needs and fluctuations of the market.

Fourth: The province needs to support farmers to further promote the international market, especially the fastidious markets. In the context of Covid-19 pandemic, the export of goods was greatly hindered. Therefore, Thai Nguyen province needs to actively negotiate and take advantage of the tax incentives from the EU-Vietnam Free Trade Agreement (EVFTA), thereby being proactive in participating in difficult markets. Calculate. Traditional markets: Middle East, South Asia, China ... need to keep the market stable, and look for new partners and minimize the dependence on a certain market. It is necessary to update the market information of partners through import markets, quickly detect and promptly resolve trade barriers to comply with agricultural commitments when participating in the WTO, ensuring Quality commitments for traditional markets and fastidious markets. This is the leading criterion for the export of goods to be favorable, improving the value of agricultural products and thereby creating a favorable setting of farmers for farmers in Thai Nguyen province.

2.2. Complete the policy of supporting property.

**** Completing education and training policies.***

Improving the quality of labor for farmers not only meets the requirements of high-tech agriculture development, but also an important factor to help farmers create appropriate livelihood strategies and get High livelihood results.

Therefore, the central government needs to issue policies on universalization in high school instead of universal at the current secondary school. This will limit middle school graduates (especially children of farmer households) participating in the labor market. Besides, from the time of school, they also need to be equipped with knowledge about law, labor law, labor discipline ... Rural young workers today are not only lacking in professional knowledge but also lack of lack of The necessary skills such as social communication, self-development ... This is a big barrier for farmers to access livelihood strategies to create high income.

The central authorities and Thai Nguyen provincial governments need to issue specific and rational policies on training for farmers. The authorities at all levels need to study the characteristics of each region, each region and each locality to have a policy of training human resources suitable for each area. It is necessary to develop training programs and technical solutions for farmers to serve science and technology transfer, apply scientific and technical advances to develop agriculture, especially high-tech agriculture.

It is necessary to coordinate closely with the human resource training institution for the agricultural sector (universities, colleges, intermediate levels) to be able to associate training and transfer of knowledge about agriculture regularly to farmers. . Regularly bringing people who are working and studying at those facilities in practice in rural areas.

Currently, the demand of human resources trained from universities, colleges and intermediate levels of agriculture, forestry and fisheries is very large, but the enrollment work faces many difficulties. Therefore, it is necessary to have policies to encourage incentives to add points to universities for children for farmers to enroll in schools of agriculture, forestry and fisheries. The amount of human resources for

rural areas. At the same time, localities need to have their preferential policies for farmers' children to return to their localities to return to the locality to contribute to the development of agricultural economy in the area. In addition, training programs of universities, colleges and intermediate schools should be aimed at building a team of professional farmers, serving the process of industrialization and modernization of rural areas. Integrating some necessary skills for future farmers in the learning environment: land management, online marketing, science and technology, smart agriculture, digital conversion.

Increasing investment in technical facilities for all levels in rural areas, creating favorable conditions for teachers to be motivated when standing in class and teaching in rural areas. There is a preferential policy to attract good teachers in this area. This is an effective solution for building a quality platform for the future farmer class of the country.

*** Completing land policy.**

To promote the effectiveness of land policy in Thai Nguyen province, the thesis proposes some of the following solutions:

Firstly, the implementation of the policy of land consolidation and large sample fields needs to be based on the characteristics of each locality in the province. The provincial authorities need to have flexible mechanisms and empower each locality to accumulate and concentrate land. Currently, land accumulation is a necessary condition to develop high -tech agriculture. With a small agricultural land, farmers do not perform mechanization and non -irrigation on their land. Therefore, farmers are in a weak position and are not equal to negotiating with businesses and can reach out to the world. In 2020, only 4 communes in Thai Nguyen province implemented the policy of land consolidation and exchange of that parcel $\frac{3}{4}$ of Phu Binh district (Thai Nguyen Party Committee, 2021).

This limitation results stemming from the provisions of the drought and for Thai Nguyen province not all district conditions also allow land consolidation and exchange of large sample fields, typically Vo Nhai district with Hill terrain with many terraced fields. In addition, it is necessary to have policies to support farmers on capital so that when implementing the policy of land consolidation and exchange, farmers do not suffer from good and bad fields.

The central government as well as the Thai Nguyen provincial government need to offer a mechanism to support and encourage land trading and transfer activities through the establishment of agricultural land banks. Connecting buyers- sellers, lessees- land renters. Without this support, it is very difficult for businesses to effectively exploit land resources. In addition, it is necessary to clearly and more officially institutionalized the relationship between the government, the people and the business when implementing the model of accumulation and concentration of land.

The People's Committee of the province and the locality need to develop a propaganda plan to raise people's awareness in participating in large sample fields, from which they take the initiative and voluntarily participate in the linkage of quality and efficiency in regulation. Land module, must be bounded and concentrated a few main rice varieties ... With the construction of a large sample field, it should be done in the area of localities with relatively good infrastructure, mechanization applications, reducing cells Truong tissue infection. The construction of a large sample field needs to be associated with building high -tech agriculture.

Second: State management agencies play the management role of the entire people, they need management tools. In the context of the current industrial revolution 4.0, the digital transformation for management is essential, the provincial government needs to be assigned to the land management agency to build a digital map, thereby integrating the entire geography. Tables, scale, soil quality, usage status, object used on a digital data platform. Thus, the construction and planning of specialized areas suitable for planting more convenient.

In the process of Industrialization Today, the recovery of a part of agricultural land to build industrial parks is indispensable. However, The People's Committee of Thai Nguyen Province Should Has Specification for each Region and Each Region, Strictly Comifolating With The Detailed Planning of Industrial Parks and Industrial Clusters and Avoid The Situation of Rampant Industrial Parks. Quickly The Land for Food Crops, Thereby Caiting National Insecurity and Affecting Farmers' Livelihoods in the process. At the same time, it is necessary to develop plans on agricultural lands for Reasonable Landing.

The compensation for resettlement for farmer households must ensure the lives of farmer households better or by the old place. People's Committees at all levels are assigned to strictly organize the bidding for agricultural, forestry and fishery land every year and thereby improve the livelihood of farmer households and socio-economic development in the locality, contributing to development. Vietnam's economy. The bidding should be organized transparently. It is necessary to check the farmer's land fund ineffective, or leave the empty agricultural land without cultivating it leading to the reception of agricultural land.

Third: The central government and the provincial government of Thai Nguyen province need policies to support the land revenue from farmer households to increase, and policy makers need to be considered and managed better. The process of changing land use purpose.

*** Completing credit policy.**

For farmer households, access to credit capital is important to promote livelihood results. Although the State and the provincial government of Thai Nguyen provincial level have many policies to remove difficulties for farmers in accessing credit capital, there are still a few limitations that make it difficult for households. Farmers approach capital. Therefore, the thesis proposes some solutions to improve credit policies, thereby improving livelihoods for farmers.

Firstly, credit institutions and localities need to review to simplify lending procedures, minimize procedures, papers and deploy many loan programs suitable to the characteristics of each business and localities and increase the linkage between processing facilities and raw material areas, such as lending contracts with the participation of four houses (farmers, processing manufacturers, export consumers, bankers).

For households without red books, the local competent authority needs to confirm the land use right and there is no dispute for farmers. The central authorities and the provincial government need to build a system of documents as a basis for farmer households to be responsible before the law for the certificate of land use rights so that households to borrow as prescribed as prescribed.

Second: Local authorities, credit institutions and banks need to have a link to support farmers to develop appropriate business projects to be able to borrow capital from collateral. At the same time, encouraging commercial banks to participate in lending to the agricultural sector, which makes the rural credit policy richer.

To encourage commercial banks to participate in lending to agriculture, rural areas, state-level governments and Thai Nguyen provincial governments need measures to develop the agricultural insurance market. The agricultural sector is a risk of many risks of natural conditions, weather, epidemics, in addition, in Vietnam, agriculture is still quite fragmented, the production scale of the agricultural sector has not been large. . Therefore, agricultural insurance is complicated and expensive, without the support from the authorities at all levels, the investment in agricultural insurance business of businesses at risk of losses is very high. Therefore, to develop the agricultural insurance market, authorities at all levels need to support agricultural insurance businesses, support businesses and farmer households through insurance premiums.

Thai Nguyen People's Committee needs to issue agricultural insurance policies by the characteristics of the province, especially the group of high-tech agricultural products: tea, cinnamon ... at the same time create opportunities for all business businesses Agricultural danger may participate in providing agricultural insurance products when they have a license and meet all operating conditions by the law. Enterprises participating in agricultural insurance business will enjoy financial encouragement mechanisms related to commission and remuneration for participants directly deploying agricultural insurance.

Third: The central government and the provincial authorities need to have policies to support interest payments in cases of risks, natural disasters, fire, floods ... Therefore, it is necessary to have flexible repayment policies flexibly For farmers when making loans instead of repayment once. The bank combined, the Farmers' Union and the farmer's households together up the effective business plan so that the livelihood results were increased, ensuring the completion of the bank's debt repayment of the households. In addition, it is necessary to have monitoring and supervision mechanisms for the use of loans from farmers, ensuring the loan for the right purpose.

Fourth: It is necessary to synchronously improve the provisions of the law related to credit policies for farmer households. The consistent construction and synchronization of the law on property rights, individual rights, business rights of individuals, businesses and financial intermediaries related to

agricultural and rural credit is the scale. In addition, these regulations need to ensure fairness between the subjects as well as other credit institutions. The law ensures the rights and clearance of the scope of activities, rights and responsibilities for financial products as the basis and premise for financial intermediaries to well perform the task of granting credit. for agriculture, rural and farmers.

2.3. Completing policies to support the conversion of livelihoods (vocational training policies).

Firstly, to make the meaning of the implementation of vocational training policies is more clearly shown, transparency is further improved, the propaganda plays a very important role. Therefore, it is necessary to have policies to support propaganda officials in improving their capacity through training and reality from which they can fully understand the information about the program and development plan. socio-economic, economic restructuring, local labor structure, grasp the information of businesses and market situation and product consumption. Such useful information will make the propaganda and vocational training advice for farmer households of Thai Nguyen province more effectively. It is necessary to diversify the forms of propaganda and especially promote the role of the Farmers' Union organization by integrating the information of vocational training policies, meaning and importance of vocational training activities in other activities. activities of the Association.

Second: The review of vocational training needs of farmers, especially members of the cooperative, production cooperative groups of all levels of government should be more active, and at the same time need to guide learners to focus on vocational training. by the socio -economic conditions of each locality; Develop planning and planning plan "Each ward of a product". The provincial government may order vocational training for key and spearhead industries suitable to the provincial conditions.

It is necessary to expand the model of agricultural vocational training associated with cooperatives, trade villages, and agriculture in rural laborers to continue promoting and applying effectively the knowledge learned into production, contributing strongly to promote strong development. Rural economic development associated with new rural construction. Farmers in Thai Nguyen province after training need to reorganize production and form effective cooperatives and cooperative development groups such as the tea village of Song Cau town of Dong Hy district; Tea craft villages in Vo Tranh commune, ie Tranh Phu Luong district ... (People's Committee of Thai Nguyen province, 2020).

Thirdly: It is necessary to mobilize the 4 levels (provincial, district, commune and vocational education level) in the inspection and supervision of the project to ensure quality and effectiveness of training. ; Especially in organizing and managing classrooms, and having a plan to manage students after vocational training, job creation, expanding loans for farmers in Thai Nguyen province to participate in vocational training To facilitate the development of the learned profession.

Fourth: Investing in facilities and equipment for vocational training activities for farmer households in Thai Nguyen province: The completion of facilities for vocational training institutions is very necessary, Supplementing equipment for vocational training activities in each locality, of which localities in extremely difficult areas need to be prioritized.

Fifth: There is a mechanism to encourage businesses to participate in vocational training activities for farmer households, directly training human resources for the company with specific local policies to support excavation costs. Create and use trained human resources.

Businesses need to be mobilized to participate in the formulation, appraisal of programs, vocational training and participation in teaching, checking and evaluating farmers in vocational classes. The construction of a training program should be closely followed with the production reality of the business so that after training farmers can catch up with the job and get the appropriate livelihood strategy.

It is necessary to have clear legal documents on land -use enterprises in the area publicly recruiting and using local labor, especially farmers.

Sixth: At present, vocational training policies have promoted certain effectiveness, and has gained the participation of all levels in implementing policies, helping policies to be more feasible. However, some farmer households have not been aware of the importance of vocational training, besides some local officials are still confused in determining the training industry. Therefore, the planning and planning of vocational training courses should be built in a methodical manner and with the consultation of experts to avoid the case of opening classes by the plan and reducing the motivation for greed. class of learners. At the same time, the use of digital platforms in developing vocational training plans for rural laborers in general and

farmers in the province in particular should be implemented and implemented. Since then, farmer households have the fastest information about classrooms.

2.4. Completing policies on ensuring livelihood results (social protection policies for farmer households).

Firstly, the propaganda of the State's and Thai Nguyen province's documents on supporting farmers when having natural disasters and epidemics should be further widely (developing a good plan but deploying it is still available. Not good, subjective within the staff). Effective propaganda will help farmers to grasp the provisions of support when having natural disasters and epidemics, thereby helping them to have plans for the implementation of production and business in the field of agriculture. Moreover, in the worst case, they also received support from the provincial government and the central government to ensure the livelihood results.

Second: Procedures to receive support need to reduce especially in terms of support time. Currently, in the study area, when there are floating dermatitis on buffaloes, cows, farmers have done procedures to receive support, however, the time to receive long support so it is difficult to cause difficulty. Towels for farmers can continue to implement next life strategies. In addition, having to wait for a long time to receive support has reduced the trust of farmer households and the reputation of local officials is more or less affected.

Third: The treatment of natural disasters and epidemics in the province has improved but still inadequate and limited. Therefore, it is necessary to have the participation of all levels and sectors, especially to enhance the role of the Farmers' Union in statistics, gathering reports, supporting natural disasters and epidemics.

Fourth: It is necessary to raise people's awareness to avoid the case of some farmers for profit but did not comply with the State's regulations: Do not destroy the number of cattle and buffaloes when they have epidemics receiving support and more importantly, it affects the health of consumers and the community.

3. Conclusion

To improve the livelihood support policy for farmers in Thai Nguyen province, the article has proposed 4 solutions: Solutions to improve the policy to support the livelihood context; perfecting support policies on livelihood assets; complete support policies on livelihood transformation; perfecting policies on ensuring livelihood outcomes.

The improvement of the livelihood support policy for farmers in Thai Nguyen province plays an important role in supporting the livelihoods of farmers. The basis of policy improvement comes from limitations and causes of limitations in policy implementation.

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